

GEOMETRICAL INSIGHTS INTO STAR-LIKE CONJUGACY ON PARTIAL INJECTIVE TRANSFORMATION SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract:

Let $X_n = \{1,2,3,\dots\}$ be a set of distinct non negative integer then $C^3\omega_n^*$ be star-like conjugacy transformation semigroup for all $D(\alpha^*)$ (domain of α^*) and $I(\alpha^*)$ (Image of α^*) such that an operator $|\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_i|$ was generated. A star-like transformation semigroup is said to satisfy collapse function if $C^+(\alpha^*) = |\text{Ut}\alpha^- : t \in T\alpha\omega_n^*|$ while the finding shows that the collapse of 3D star-like conjugacy classes are zero. The geometry model of 3D starlike conjugacy was obtained by using folding principle on a standard A4 paper which shows the star-like 3D conjugacy relation $\alpha^{(ij)} = \frac{\alpha_i + \alpha_{i+1}}{\alpha_i - \alpha_{i+1}} = \frac{\alpha_{i+1} + \alpha_i}{\alpha_{i+1} - \alpha_i}$. Some tables were formed to analyse the structure of star-like derank of $C^3\omega_n^*$ be $|n - \text{Im}\alpha^*| = d$, star-like collapse $C^+(\alpha^*) = |\text{Ut}\alpha^- : t \in T\alpha\omega_n^*|$, Star-like relapse $C^-(\alpha^*) = |n - C^+(\alpha^*)|$, Star-like pivot of $C^3\omega_n^*$

Be $|\frac{n.r^+(\alpha^*)}{c(\alpha^*) + c^1(\alpha^*)}| = p$ and Star-like joint of $C^3\omega_n^*$ be $|r^+(\alpha^*) - m^*(\alpha^*) - C^+(\alpha^*) + n| = j$. The study conclude that $C^3\omega_n^*$ has n order conjugacy classes and we show that $\alpha \in C^3\omega_n^*$.

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1 Introduction

Group theory continues to be an intensively studied matter. There are three historical roots of group theory: the theory of algebraic equation, number theory and geometry. Joseph Louis Lagrange, Niels Henrik Abel and Evariste Galois were early researchers in the late 18th century. While semigroup started in the early 1930s with the work of [4]. The star-like partial one-one transformation semigroup denoted as $I\alpha\omega_n^*$ in I_n is also a semigroup in one-one transformation semigroup, see [7]. Transformation is used instead of mapping, the latter serves as another name for the former. More information on semigroup of transformation are obtainable from the works of [5, 6]. The domain and image set of any given transformations $\alpha_i^* \in \alpha\omega_n^*$

was denoted by $D(\alpha^*)$ and $I(\alpha^*)$ respectively as used by [3]. A Star-like transformation semigroup is said to satisfy collapse function if $c^+(\alpha^*) = |\text{St}\alpha^- : t \in T\alpha\omega_n^*|$ while Relapse function is denoted as $C^-(\alpha) = |n - c^+(\alpha^*)|$ where $n \in N$ see [8]. Any transformation $\alpha \in \omega_n$ defined in the operator $|\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_i|$, is a mapping from a set to itself such that the star-like composition of any two or more transformation of the same set gives the same transformation of this set. Therefore the composition $\alpha \in \alpha\omega_n$ is a special case of $\alpha\omega_n$.

Consider some elements of α such that

$$\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} K_1 & K_2 & K_3 & \dots & K_n \\ \alpha^* K_1 & \alpha^* K_2 & \alpha^* K_3 & \dots & K_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.1)$$

The set of all-star-like transformation of $\alpha\omega_n$ on X_n would be denoted as α_i . Therefore, the elements of α in the transformation has the form

$$\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & \dots & n \\ \alpha^* \omega_1 & \alpha^* \omega_2 & \alpha^* \omega_3 & \dots & \alpha \omega_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.2)$$

Thus, the transformation to find in succession $\alpha(i,j)$ special entries of ω_n , was established such that when we consider an element of order four in $\alpha\omega_n \leq \omega_n$

$$\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1\alpha & 2\alpha & 3\alpha & 4\alpha \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.3)$$

with domain $D(\alpha) = (1,2,3,4)$ and image set $I(\alpha) = (1\alpha, 2\alpha, 3\alpha, 4\alpha)$ we obtain a general star-like recurrence relations.

The star-like pivot of α^* is denoted and defined as $V^+(\alpha^*) = \lfloor \frac{n \cdot r^+(\alpha^*)}{c^+(\alpha^*) + c^-(\alpha^*)} \rfloor$. The star-like joint of α^* is denoted and defined as $J^+(\alpha^*) = |r^+(\alpha^*) - m^*(\alpha^*) - C^+ + n|$. The star-like relapse of α^* is denoted and defined as $c^-(\alpha^*) = |n - c^+(\alpha^*)|$. Star-like collapse of α^* is denoted by $c^+(\alpha^*)$ and defined as $c^+(\alpha^*) = |\bigcup_{i=1}^n y_i \alpha^{-1*} : |y_i \alpha^{-1*}| \geq 2|$.

2 Preliminary Notes

The study of [1, 2] exhibit some properties which formed the bases of this research and these properties will be discuss in this section which will help us to formulate our results

3 Generalization of 3-Dimensional star – like sequences through some combinatorial composite functions

Definition 3.1. Conjugacy: *It is a set of element that are connected by an operation that is in group (G) then the element (a) and (b) are conjugate of each other if their is another element (g) in (G) such that $b = gbg^{-1}$*

Definition 3.2. *Let $X_n = \{1,2,3,\dots\}$ be a non empty finite set, and $C^3\omega_n^*$ be a 3 D star-like Conjugacy transformation semigroups, such that*

$$|\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{(i+1)}| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_i| \quad (3.1)$$

For all $\omega_i \in D(\alpha^)$ and $\alpha^* \omega_i \in I(\alpha^*)$, where $N_i \cup \emptyset$; $N_i = i, i+1, i+2, \dots, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$*

We investigate the star-like 3 D model using folding principles on A4 paper see definition 2.1 of [1]. The star-like 3D model in Fig. 1 represent the star-like conjugacy rectangular prism with the composition of:

1. Star-like faces F^*
2. Star-like edges E^*
3. Star-like vertices V^*

Figure 1: Star-like Conjugacy triangular Prism

By the star-like folding principle structure we unfold the Fig. 1 to obtain the general 3D star-like conjugacy equation.

$$F^* + V^* = E^* + 2 \quad (3.2)$$

Which is a relation to the unfolded 3D star-like conjugacy rectangular prism. Therefore to obtain the volume of a 3D star-like conjugacy triangular prism V , we must begin to construct a starlike triangular path with a 3D star-like conjugacy array of a control star-like conjugacy disk point which form an n sided star-like conjugacy 3D depths. From equation 3.1 combining with 3D general star-like conjugacy, we obtained

$$V = \frac{1}{2} b \times h \times l \quad (3.3)$$

Equivalent to

$$\frac{1}{2} V = |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_i| \quad (3.4)$$

where $\omega_{i+1} \in D(\alpha^*)$ and $\alpha\omega_i \in I(\alpha^*)$, to generate:

Figure 2: Unfolded Star-like Conjugacy triangular Prism

Lemma 3.1. Let $C^3\omega_n^*$ be set of star-like conjugacy classes, with $\alpha^* \in \frac{L^* + F^*}{2} + \phi^*$ then $D(\alpha^*) \subseteq$

$I(\alpha^*)$ such that $L^* \in D(C^3\omega_n^*)$ and $F^* \in I(C^3\omega_n^*)$.

Proof. Suppose $C^3\omega_n^*$ be set of star-like conjugacy transformation semigroup with a star-like composite relation.

$$a*i + b*j + c*k = C3\omega n^* \quad (3.5)$$

There exist $i(2) = \phi^*$ for $C\omega_n^* \in \alpha\omega_n^*$.

By general 3D conjugacy and star-like operator

$$F^* + V^* = E^* + 2 \quad (3.6)$$

yields

$$\frac{E^* - F^*}{2} = |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \leq |\alpha\omega_{i+1} - \omega_i| \quad (3.7)$$

Then, $C^3\omega_n^*$ satisfy eqn (3.1) and eqn (3.2) we see that $V^*(C^3\omega_n^*) = \frac{E^* - F^*}{2} + \phi^*$ which is the required conjugacy vertices for any $\alpha^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ with a star-like conjugacy disk constant point $\phi^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$.

Lemma 3.2. Let $S^*(x,y)$ represent order of sequences from the star-like origin $(0,0)^*$ to $(x,y)^*$ with star-like row- x and column- y then $\alpha_i^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ form a star-like triangular array.

Proof. Suppose $\alpha_i^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ with row- x and column- y of triangular star-like sequences for all $N_i = \{i, i + 1, i + 2, \dots\}, (i = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$.

Then for any $\alpha_i^* \in C^3\omega_n^*(i = 1, \dots)$ we obtain the star-like conjugacy operations

$$S^*(x,0) = X_i^* S^*(0,y) = Y_i^*$$

Such that $X_i^* = Y_i^* = \phi^* \in C\omega_n^*$

Therefore,

$$S^*(x,y) = S^*(x,y - X_i^*) + S^*(x - Y_i^*, y) \quad (3.8)$$

yields a star-like conjugacy sequential recurrence order

$$\binom{x+y}{x}^* + \binom{x+y}{y}^* = \frac{x+y}{x!y!} \quad (3.9)$$

with star-like row- x and column- y ; $x_i \in X_i^*$ and $y_i \in Y_i^* : N_i = \{i, i + 1, \dots\}$. \square

4 Geometry Model on the 3D Star-like Transformation

. A star-like 3D conjugacy triangular pyramid is a star-like polyhedron with $9(F^*)$, a $12(E^*)$, and all other $5(V^*)$ star-like conjugacy polyhedron meeting at a star-like disk point which was embedded in equation (3.4). The geometry model of 3D star-like conjugacy triangular pyramid was obtained from the generalization of the 3D star-like conjugacy sequence of both the bottom and front view respectively as shown in Fig.4

Figure 3: Star-like 3D star-like square pyramid of [1]

Figure 4: Double View of 3D square pyramid

Which shows the star-like 3D conjugacy relation

$$\alpha(i, j) = \frac{\alpha_i + \alpha(i+1)}{\alpha_i - \alpha(i+1)} = \frac{\alpha(i+1) + \alpha(i)}{\alpha(i+j) - \alpha(j)} \quad (4.1)$$

That is, by the proof of theorem 3.3 of [1] the star-like 3D conjugacy prism is an equivalence relations, so the distinct star-like conjugacy class's transformation, which means that $C^3\omega_n^*$ has n order conjugacy classes.

Lemma 4.1. Let $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ be a star-like conjugacy spinnable transformation then if $\exists U^* \in \zeta$, $pq \overset{\Delta}{\rightleftharpoons} rs$

such that $|\Delta pqr| \leq |\Delta qrs|$ for all $pqr \in U_n^*$

Proof. Suppose $U_n^* \leq \zeta$

Then for any $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ there must exist an equilateral star-like shape such that ζ^* is a conjugacy spinnable. Consider

where, the star-like folding principle is adopted and by eqn (3.5) we see that for any $p_i \in \zeta^*$ in above figure there exist a constant disk point $i(2) \in N$ with adjacent equal star-like side $pqr \in U_n^*$. Then

$$|\Delta pqr| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \quad (4.2)$$

$$|\Delta qrs| \leq |\alpha_{i+1} - \omega_i| \quad (4.3)$$

Therefore by conjugacy operator in eqn (3.5)

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$$|\Delta pqs| \leq |\Delta qrs| \quad (4.4)$$

Which shows that $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ any conjugate spinnable star-like transformation, the converse makes equal star-like angle on all side. \square

5 Main Results

Table 1: Rellapse Table of the Image of $C^3\omega_n^*$ $C^-(\alpha^*) = |n - C^+(\alpha^*)|$

$n/C^-(\alpha)$	1	2	3	4	5	${}^pF(n;d)$
1	2					2
2		3				3
3			5			5
4				6		6
5					6	6

Lemma 5.1. Given that $\alpha \in C^3\omega_n^*$ is spinnable reducible then $|C^+(\alpha^*)| \leq |C^-(\alpha^*)|$ whenever

$$|C^3\omega_n^*| = \binom{\frac{d^2}{n} - (2+n)}{d-q}$$

Proof. :

Let $X_n = \{1,2,3,\dots\}$ be a non negative star-like set, such that $F(n,d,q) = |C^3\omega_n|$. Since $D(C^+(\alpha^*)) \subseteq X_n$ and $I(C^-(\alpha^*)) \subseteq X_n$ with $M(\alpha^*) \in C^3\omega_n^*$ of a domain in a star-like point of X_n

is chosen from $\binom{d}{q}$ methods then in each star-like partial conjugacy bijection . We have

$$C^3\omega_n^*(\alpha^*) : DC^+(\alpha^*) \rightarrow IC^-(\alpha^*)$$

. Suppose $C^3\omega_n^*$ is rellapsible under the composition of star-like conjugacy mapping where $\alpha^* \in$

$$C^3\omega_n^*, f(n,d,q) = \binom{\frac{d^2}{n} - (2+n)}{d-q}$$

Then, by the star-like operator in eqn (3.1) which compels the conjugacy element of a star-like partial one-one is reducible. Therefore by lemme 3.2, a star-like conjugacy spinnable transformation exist and such that $|\Delta pqr| \leq |\Delta qrs|$ we show that

$$|C^+(\alpha)| \leq |C^-(\alpha)| \leq |\alpha\omega_i - \omega_{i+1}| \quad (5.1)$$

Which makes every star-like conjugacy transformation $\alpha \in C^3\omega_n^*$ to produce a collapsible and reducible algebraic structure and makes equal star-like point on all side so that whenever $|d| = |q|$

the $|C^3\omega_n^*| = \binom{\frac{d^2}{n} - (2+n)}{d-q}$ for all $d \geq q \geq n \geq 2$

Hence , the result is complete as shown table 1 \square

Table 2: Derank Table of the Image of $C^3\omega_n^*$ $D(\alpha^*) = |n - Im\alpha^*| = d$

n/d	1	2	3	4	5	${}^pF(n;d)$
1	1					1
2	1					1
3	3					3
4	4					4
5	4					4

Table 3: Pivot Tab of the Image of $C^3\omega_n^*$ $D(\alpha^*) = \frac{n.r^+(\alpha^*)}{C^-(\alpha^*) + C^+(\alpha^*)} = p$

n/p	1	2	3	4	5	$PF(n;p)$
1	1					1
2	1	2				3
3		3	2			5
4			4	2		6
5				3	3	6

Table 4: Joint Table of the Image of $C^3\omega_n^*$ $D(\alpha^*) = |r^+(\alpha^*) - m^*(\alpha^*) - C^+(\alpha^*) + n| = j$

n/j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	$PF(n;j)$
1	1										1
2		1	1	1							3
3			1	2	2						5
4				1		2	2	1			6
5	4				1			2	2	1	6

Proposition 5.1

Let X_n be a star-like non-negative generated integer such that $Dom(C^3\omega_n^*) = \sum_{j=1}^n X_n$. Then for

any given $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ $| \alpha^* C^3\omega_n^* | = \binom{j+1}{n+1} \binom{n+j}{2j}$.

Proof. :

Given that $\zeta^* \leq Dom(C^3\omega_n^*) \leq X_n$ and $C^3\omega_n^* \subseteq \alpha\omega_n^*$, then

$f(n, j) = | \alpha^* \in \alpha^*\omega_n^* : C^3\omega_n^*(\alpha^*) = \alpha C^3\omega_n^* | |$.

Consider $j = | j = | r^+(\alpha) - m^*(\alpha) + C^+(\alpha) + n |$ such that here exist $k_0 \in Dom(C^3\omega_n^*)$. Equation (3.1) produce a star-like joint $\alpha k_0 = e^0$ so k_0 has $n - e^0 + 1$ star-like order for all $n \geq j \geq 1$.

$\binom{n+j}{2j}$. Since ζ^* is a star-like spinnable transformation, $\emptyset(\zeta^*)$ is a star-like sub-set of all star-like

joint $j^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$, irrespective of the value of $n \geq j \geq 1$, whenever $j = (n - 1)$ there is exactly finitely many star-like conjugacy composite classes of nth order such that by table 4 and equation

(3.5) $| \alpha^* C^3\omega_n^* | = \binom{j+1}{n+1} \binom{n+j}{2j}$ for all $n \geq j \geq 1$ generate a star-like sequence array. \square

Lemma 5.2. Let $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ then $| C(\alpha^*) | = \binom{a-b}{b-1} = \binom{a-(b-1)}{a-b} = | r(\alpha^*) |$ for all

$a, b, \in \zeta^* \leq C^3\omega_n^*$.

Proof. Suppose $X_n = \{1, 2, \dots\}$ be a non degenerated star-like integers, then $Dom(C(\alpha^*)) =$

$Dom(r(\alpha^*)) = \sum_{i=1}^n X_n$

If $f(a, b) = | \zeta^* : h(\zeta^*) | = | Im(\zeta^*) | = b$ there exist $K_0 \in X_n$ such that

$\zeta^* k_0 = \zeta_n^* = \zeta^* k_0$ (5.2)

so $\zeta^* k_0 = e^0$ (a star-like conjugacy constant).

Since k_0 has $a - e^0 + 1$ disk point degree of freedom with equal order of collapse and rollapse then,

$| C(\alpha^*) | = | r(\alpha^*) |$ (5.3)

$\binom{a-b}{b-1} = \binom{a-(b-1)}{a-1} = e^0$

(5.4)

For any star-like conjugacy transformation with $\zeta^* \in C^3\omega_n^*$ $h(\zeta^*) = e^0$ irrespective of the value of $C(\alpha^*)$ and $r(\alpha^*)$ whenever

$$\zeta^* k_0 = \zeta_n^* \quad (5.5)$$

Therefore

$$\begin{pmatrix} a-b \\ b-1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a-(b-1) \\ a-b \end{pmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b \in \zeta^+ \leq C^3 \omega_n^*. \quad \square$$

6 Conclusion

In this paper, We showed that the geometric characterization of star-like 3D conjugacy classes $C^3 \omega_n^*$ on partial one-one transformation semigroups and some results of different functions. The paper conclude that for every 3D star-like conjugacy classes $C^3 \omega_n^*$ has n order conjugacy classes and we also show that

$$\phi \in C^3 \omega_n^*$$

References

- A. Ibrahim, M. M. Mogbonju, A.O. Adeniji S. A. Akinwunmi,(2023), Angular loop model of 3 dimensional ALM transformation semigroup. International Journal of Mathematical Science and Optimization: Theory and Application. 9(2):13 -22.
- Ibrahim, A., Akinwunmi, S.A., Mogbonju, M.M., and Onyeozili, I.A., (2024), combinatorial model of 3 dimensional nildempotency star-like class's $N_n \omega_n^*$ partial one-one semigroups. International Journal of Mathematical Science and Optimization: Theory and Application 10(1):25-35.
- Malik, D.S., Mordeson, N.J. and Sen, M. K (2007), Introduction to Abstract Algebra. Scientific word publisher, United State of America. 6(1):101-103.
- Clifford, A. H., (1992), Union of group, semigroup theory and its applications. New Orlen LA (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. 5-14
- Howie, J.M.,(2006), Monograph on semigroup of mappings. School of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Saint Andrews, North Haught, United Kingdom. 86:33-40
- Bhattacharya P.B., Jaini, S.K. and Nagpaul, S.R. (2018), First course in linear algebra.New age International Publisher. London, New-delhi, Nairobi.
- Akinwunmi, S. A. Mogbonju, M. M. and Adeniji, A. O. (2018), Multiplicative invertibility characterizations on star-like cyclicpoid $C_y P \omega_n^*$ finite partial transformation semigroups Hikari Journal of Pure Mathematical Science. 10 (1):45-55.
- Ibrahim, G. R, Lawal, O. J, Akinwumi, S. A, Bakare, G. N and Adeshola, A. D. (2022) , Some Combinatorial Results on Star-Like Transformation Semigroups. Nigerian Journal of Mathematics and Applications. 32:56-67